

STRUCTURAL DESIGN OF CONFORMAL LOAD BEARING ANTENNA STRUCTURE (CLAS) (PART I)

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1 Introduction

The Conformal Load Bearing Antenna Structure (CLAS) is a new multidisciplinary concept of aircraft structure which combines structural and electrical functions to the one structural component. The fundamental design concept of CLAS is an integral composite structure, in which a microstrip antenna is layered into a composite structure.

Recently, Korean government and industries have been interested in CLAS. The structural function of CLAS is load-bearing member of aircraft and its electrical function is antenna for communication and navigation of the aircraft. To satisfy those requirements, CLAS can be used both structural and electrical function. In addition to that, CLAS can reduce the RCS (Radar Cross Section) and drag for next generation stealth aircraft.

When it comes to cost of CLAS, it has low cost of maintenance including MRO (Maintenance, Repair and Overhaul) stage of the aircraft operation by substitution of conventional blade antenna.

This overall study proposes CLAS that contains communication and navigation antenna in one external smart skin of the aircraft.

2 Design and Analysis Procedure

The CLAS to be dealt with in this study has a sandwich construction for light weight without sacrificing strength. As a multidisciplinary member, OML (Outer Mold Line) side of face sheet withstands tension and compression loading and is used as a radome of antenna. The core withstands shear loading and contains radiating element that transmits and receives RF (Radio Frequency) signal for communication and navigation of the aircraft.

The Fig.1. and Tab.1. illustrates the layered CLAS construction where many parts play a dual structural and electrical role.

After an initial design to withstand required specification, structural analysis was performed to verify the load carrying capability using a commercial FEA (Finite Element Analysis) code, MSC/Nastran. The shell element (pcomp card in MSC/Nastran) was used to model the layered face sheet, radiating element, core and housing. The solution sequence 101 (linear static), 103 (normal mode) and 105 (buckling) of MSC/Nastran, were used for structural analysis, respectively.

Tab.1. CLAS Parts

Parts	Material
Conductive Mesh	Copper Mesh
Face Sheet	GFRP UD
Radiating Element	Antenna impregnated plastic.
Core	Nomex Honeycomb
Housing	CFRP Fabric

Fig.1. CLAS Configuration

From the first structural analysis on initial design, some modifications were made for structurally weak areas and RF transmission requirements of antenna. The final structural configuration was fixed through several iteration of design loop. The Fig.2. shows the design loop of CLAS.

Fig.2. CLAS Design Loop

3 Structural Analysis

3.1 Mechanical Property

Mechanical properties for CLAS were obtained from coupon test data. These data were used as input data of structural analysis and assessment of fabrication process.

Fig.3. Coupon Test for Housing (Compression)

Procedure for calculating statistically-based material properties are cited from Chapter 8 of MIL-HDBK-17 Volume 1. [5]

That describes computational methods for obtaining A- and B-basis values from composite material coupon test data.

For a conservative approach, A-basis value was used in this study. A-basis means a 95% lower confidence bound on the first percentile of a specified population of measurements.

$$A = \bar{x} - k_A s \quad (1)$$

A : A allowable (A-basis value)

\bar{x} : Average value for normal distribution

k_A : One-sided A-basis tolerance limit factor for normal distribution

s : Standard deviation for normal distribution

The k_A value was cited from Tab.8.5.11 of MIL-HDBK-17 Volume 1. [5]

The result of A-basis value of housing is in Tab.2.

Tab.2. Coupon Test Results for Housing

Property		Value	Spec.(ASTM)
Tensile 0°	Modulus	61.50 GPa	D3039
	Strength	691.2 MPa	
	Poisson's ratio	0.057	
Tensile 90°	Modulus	61.33 GPa	D3039
	Strength	621.6 MPa	
	Poisson's ratio	0.050	
Compression 0°	Strength	464.8 MPa	D695
In-Plane Shear	Modulus	3.733 GPa	D5379
	Strength	66.68 MPa	
Flexural 0°	Modulus	66.72 GPa	D790
	Strength	833.6 MPa	
Interlamina Shear	Strength	65.68 MPa	D2344

Mechanical properties of face sheet, radiating element and core were cited from data sheet of manufacturer. [6][7][8]

Detailed mechanical properties will be obtained from further coupon test.

3.2 Stress Analysis

To perform the stress analysis, MSC/Nastran was used for finite element analysis. In this analysis, the linear static analysis was carried out under compression and shear loading condition. The intra-lamina failure index of ‘Tsai-Hill’ theory was used to find structural safety. The boundary condition was assumed that the edges are fixed to simulate fastener fixed aircraft skin condition.

Tab.3. Stress Analysis Result

Parts	Failure Index	
	Compression	Shear
Face Sheet	0.292	0.903
Radiating Element	0.007	0.001
Core	0.007	0.001
Housing	0.018	0.103
Max. Displacement	0.386 mm	0.146 mm

(a) Compression Loading

(b) Shear Loading

Fig.4. Stress Analysis Result

According to the stress analysis result, current design has enough strength for given loading condition.

3.3 Buckling Analysis

To perform the buckling analysis, MSC/Nastran was used for finite element analysis. In this analysis, the buckling analysis was carried out under compression loading condition. The boundary condition was assumed that two opposite edges are fixed to simulate fastener fixed aircraft skin condition. Remaining two edges were left free boundary condition for conservative approach.

Tab.4. Buckling Analysis Result

	Axial Load
Buckling Load Factor	7.048

Fig.5. Buckling Mode Shape of CLAS

According to the buckling analysis result, current design has enough strength for given buckling condition.

3.4 Modal Analysis

To perform the modal analysis, MSC/Nastran was used for finite element analysis. In this analysis, the normal mode analysis was carried out under fixed boundary condition to simulate fastener fixed aircraft skin condition.

Tab.5. Buckling Analysis Result

	Mode 1	Mode 2	Mode 3	Mode 4
Frequency (Hz)	424.9	631.6	752.5	895.3

Fig.6. First Mode Shape of CLAS

Tab.5. shows the lower four frequencies, respectively. The possibility of resonance due to flight vibration environment was investigated, and each mode of CLAS does not make a resonance with flight vibration environment.

4 Test Plan

In order to verify the structural integrity of CLAS, coupon, element and full-scale test will be performed.

4.1 Coupon Test

Mechanical properties for CLAS will be obtained from coupon test specification as shown in Tab.2. In case of face sheet and housing, lamina test was used to evaluate the properties of the fiber and matrix together in the composite form.

Coupon test was completed for housing and test will be performed for face sheet. Coupon test for radiating element will be done by specification for plastic. [9][10] Mechanical property for core will be derived from element test data.

4.2 Element Test

This test will be performed to evaluate the mechanical properties CLAS as a sandwich structure.

Like other composite structure development, the design development and test will be performed concurrently. In this CLAS test, element test will be done for sandwich structure as shown in Tab.6.

Tab.6. Element Test for CLAS

Test	Spec. (ASTM)	Mechanical Property
Flatwise Tension	C297	Core tensile strength or face sheet/housing to core bonding strength
Flatwise Compression	C365	Flatwise compressive properties of sandwich core
Edgewise Compression	C364	Edgewise compressive strength
Core Shear	C393	Core shear properties of sandwich construction by beam flexure
Shear Fatigue	C394	Shear fatigue of sandwich core material

4.3 Full Scale Test

For CLAS, full scale test will be done for compression and shear loading conditions as shown in Fig.7. CLAS will be fixed in the test jig by using fasteners.

Fig.7. Full Scale Test for CLAS

For each loading condition, final evaluation for structural integrity will be verified for design requirements on CLAS.

5 Conclusion

In this design and analysis, structural integrity verification for proposed CLAS was performed. Through the verification, it was confirmed that the final design has sufficient strength and stiffness for stress, buckling and resonance.

In addition to that, the prototype of CLAS will be manufactured and tested for evaluation of structural integrity.

This paper deals with structural design and analysis of CLAS. The comparison between analysis and test will be dealt on the part II paper.

References

- [1] E. F. Bruhn “*Analysis and Design of Flight Vehicle Structures*”. 1st edition, Tri-State Offset Company, 1973.
- [2] Michael Chun-Yung Niu “*Composite Airframe Structures*”. 2nd edition, Hong Kong Conmilit Press, 1996.
- [3] B. C. Hoskin and A. A. Baker “*Composite Materials for Aircraft Structures*”. AIAA Education Series, 1986.
- [4] F. C. Campbell “*Manufacturing Technology for Aerospace Structural Materials*”. First edition, ELSEVIER, 2006.
- [5] Department of Defense “*MIL-HDBK-17-1F Volume 1. Polymer Matrix Composites Guidelines for Characterization of Structural Materials*”. 2002.
- [6] Tencate Technical Data “*RS-36 Resin System*”. Tencate Advanced Composites USA, Inc., 2011.
- [7] LG Chemical Technical Data “*LUPOX Injection Moldings*”. LG Chemical Inc.s, 2009.
- [8] The Engineering Society for Advancing Mobility Land Sea Air and Space “*AMS 3711E Core, Honeycomb Fibrous, Aramid Base, Phenolic Coated*”. 2001.
- [9] The American Society for Testing and Materials “*ASTM D638 Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Plastics*”. 2010.
- [10] The American Society for Testing and Materials “*ASTM D790 Standard Test Methods for Flexural Properties of Unreinforced and Reinforced Plastics and Electrical Insulating Materials*”. 2010.